

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON THE FREQUENCY OF ANTI-TUBERCULOUS THERAPY INDUCED HEPATITIS¹Muhammad Umair, ²Muhammad Faizan Akram, ³Muhammed Hamza Hassan Qadri
¹Mayo Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study was to determine the frequency of anti-tuberculous therapy (ATT) induced hepatitis.

Methodology: This was a descriptive study and was carried out at Mayo Hospital Lahore from May 2020 to September 2020. In this study the cases of known Tuberculosis were included. Anti-Tuberculosis Therapy included Isoniazid, Rifampicin Ethambutol and Pyrazinamide according to standard WHO recommended doses. The cases suffering from hepatitis B, C or HIV or those with derange liver functions were excluded from this study. The cases were followed weekly and Liver function tests (LFTs) were performed and hepatitis was labelled as yes where there was rise in liver enzymes three times upper limit with symptoms (nausea/vomiting/abdominal pain) or 5 times without any symptoms. The final outcome was seen at 4 weeks.

Results: In this study there were total 80 cases of TB out of which 60 (60%) were males and 20 (20%) females. The mean age of the subjects was 36.9 ± 9.43 years. There were 68 cases with pulmonary and 12 had EPTB. ATT induced hepatitis was observed in 4 (4%) of the cases. ATT induced hepatitis was significantly high in males affecting 3 (5.12%) cases with p value of 0.04. There was no significant difference in terms of weight groups with $p= 0.68$. Hepatotoxicity was more seen in cases having EPTB where 2 out of 12 cases had it; although this difference was statistically not significant with $p=0.13$.

Conclusion: Anti-tuberculous therapy (ATT) induced hepatitis is uncommon but is seen significantly high in male gender.

Keywords: Anti-Tuberculous Therapy, Hepatitis, Pyrazinamide, Hepatotoxicity, Rifampicin Ethambutol

Corresponding author:

Muhammad Umair,
Mayo Hospital Lahore.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Umair et al, A Descriptive Study On The Frequency Of Anti-Tuberculous Therapy Induced Hepatitis., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis (TB) is a disease of ancient times and is one of the most common infectious diseases. It is more prevalence in developing countries but number is increasing in the developed ones due to emergence of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) [1]. The prevalence in Pakistan is 231 per 100,000 population. It can involve any organ of the body and the treatment is the same and have combination of chemotherapeutic agents and include Isoniazid (H), Rifampicin (R), Pyrazinamide (Z), and Ethambutol (E) and among these first three agents are considered as hepatotoxic. Pyrazinamide is the most culprit drug and has this incidence rate of hepatitis in 9% of the cases while Isoniazid had this in 3% and Rifampicin in 1% of the cases [2]. There are different risk factors that can predispose to this and include male gender, previous viral hepatitis in the form of hepatitis B, C and HIV, alcoholism and concomitant use of hepatotoxic drugs. The frequency of hepatitis varies from 3 to 29% in different studies, while in Pakistan multiple studies show 3 to 9% only.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a descriptive case series and was carried out at Mayo Hospital Lahore from May 2020 to September 2020. In this study the cases of known Tuberculosis were included. Anti-Tuberculosis Therapy included Isoniazid, Rifampicin Ethambutol

and Pyrazinamide according to standard WHO recommended doses. The cases suffering from hepatitis B, C or HIV or those with derange liver functions were excluded from this study. The cases were followed weekly and Liver function tests (LFTs) were performed and hepatitis was labelled as yes where there was rise in liver enzymes three times upper limit with symptoms (nausea/vomiting/abdominal pain) or 5 times without any symptoms. The final outcome was seen at 4 weeks. The data was analyzed by SPSS-Version 22. Effect modifier were stratified and post stratification Chi-Square test was applied taking P-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

In this study there were total 80 cases of TB out of which 60 (60%) were males and 20 (20%) females. The mean age of the subjects was 36.09 ± 9.43 years. There were 68 cases with pulmonary and 12 had EPTB. ATT induced hepatitis was observed in 4 (4%) of the cases. ATT induced hepatitis was significantly high in males affecting 3 (5.12%) cases with p value of 0.04 as shown in table I. There was no significant difference in terms of weight groups with $p=0.68$ (table II). Hepatotoxicity was more seen in cases having EPTB where 2 out of 12 cases had it; although this difference was statistically not significant with $p=0.13$ as in table III.

Table I: ATT Induced Hepatitis Vs Gender

Gender	ATT Induced Hepatitis		Total	p value
	Yes	No		
Male	3 (5.12%)	55 (74.88%)	60	0.04
Female	1 (1.11%)	21 (78.89%)	20	
Total	4 (4%)	76 (76%)	80	

Table II: ATT Induced Hepatitis Vs Weight

Weight	ATT Induced Hepatitis		Total	p value
	Yes	No		
<40	2 (4.13%)	49 (75.87%)	53	0.68
>40	2 (5.12%)	31 (74.88%)	27	
Total	4 (4%)	76 (76%)	80	

Table III: ATT Induced Hepatitis Vs Type Of TB

Type of TB	ATT Induced Hepatitis		Total	p value
	Yes	No		
Pulmonary TB	2 (5.13%)	64 (74.87%)	68	0.13
EPTB*	2 (7.07%)	12 (72.93%)	12	
Total	4 (4%)	76 (76%)	80	

*EPTB= Extra pulmonary TB

DISCUSSION:

Tuberculosis is itself a fatal condition as it can affect any organ of the body and need an intensive course of chemotherapeutic agents in the form of ATT which are not spare of side effect profiles [3,4]. ATT induced hepatitis is a salient entity as it can alter the course of treatment and the choice of drugs to lesser effective drugs and ultimately can result in drug resistance emergence. In the present study [5,6], ATT induced hepatitis was seen in 4 (4%) of the cases. there is wide diversity in the prevalence of ATT induced hepatitis globally and it ranges from 1 to 61% [7]. This can be explained by multiple factors i.e., difference in the operational definitions, presence of viral hepatitis in the inclusion criteria, alcoholism and different acetylator status in different populations etc [8]. But majority of the studies revoked this occurrence in 3 -9% of the cases [9].

ATT induced hepatitis was significantly high in males affecting 3 (5.12%) cases with p value of 0.04. This was also proved in the past that male gender is an independent risk factor to have drug induced hepatitis [10,11]. Various studies have shown that males have the highest number of cases with ATT induced hepatitis; few had significant and others non-significant association with this [12]. Hepatotoxicity was more seen in cases having EPTB where 2 out of 12 cases had it; although this difference was statistically not significant with p=0.13 [13,14]. There were conflicting results and it was seen that this was more common in cases of pulmonary TB. while others revealed this more in cases with extra pulmonary TB. But none of these studies find any significant association with this.

CONCLUSION:

Anti-tuberculous therapy (ATT) induced hepatitis is uncommon but is seen significantly high in male gender.

REFERENCES:

1. Singh MK, Mamatha S, Jain R, Jha AK, Nigam SK. Incidence and risk factors for hepatitis in patients receiving anti tuberculosis treatment. *J Evo Med and Dent Sci.* 2013;02(1):01-08.
2. Tariq S, Khan TS, Malik S, Anwar MS, Rashid A. Frequency of anti-tuberculous therapy-induced hepatotoxicity in patients and their outcome. *J Ayub Med coll Abbott.* 2009;21(4):50-52.
3. Haq MU, Rasul S, Khan SU, Saeed S, Tahir TM. Anti-Tuberculosis drug induced hepatitis. *Pak J Chest Med.* 2001;7(5):41-45.
4. Haq MU, Rasul S, Iqbal ZH, Chaudhary MK, Bhatti AH, Anwar N, et al. Incidence of Hepatitis in patients taking antituberculosis treatment. *Ann King Edward Med Coll.* 1996;2(3):49-51.
5. Shaikh MA, Yakta DE, Shaikh D. Frequency of Hepatotoxicity during anti-tuberculosis treatment at Medical Unit of LUHMS Sindh. *Med Chann.* 2012;18(1):20-23.
6. Anand AC, Seth AK, Paul M, Puri P. Risk Factors of hepatotoxicity during anti-tuberculosis treatment. *Med J Armed Forces Ind.* 2006;62(1):45-49.
7. Crofton J, Seaton A, Seaton D, Leitch AG. *Crofton and Douglas's Respiratory Diseases.* 5th ed. Oxford: Blackwell;2000.
8. Singla R, Sharma SK, Mohan A, Makharia G, Sreenivas V, Jha B, et al. Evaluation of risk factors for antituberculosis treatment induced hepatotoxicity. *Ind J Med Res.* 2010;132(7):81-86.
9. WHO. Treatment of tuberculosis: Guidelines for national tuberculosis control program. 4th ed. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2008.
10. McPherson RA, Pincus MR. *Henry's Clinical Diagnosis and Management by Laboratory Methods.* 22nd ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders; 2011.
11. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC); American Thoracic Society. Update: adverse event data and revised American Thoracic Society/CDC recommendations against

- the use of rifampin and pyrazinamide for treatment of latent tuberculosis infection—United States, 2003. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2003; 52:735–9.
12. Singh J, Garg PK, Tandon RK . Hepatotoxicity due to antituberculosis therapy; clinical profile and reintroduction of therapy. J Clin Gastroenterol. 1996;22(3):211-4.
 13. Ansari S, Bawany MA, Hayat AS, Munir A, Khahro AA, Naz F. drug induced hepatitis; does hepatitis B and hepatitis C co-infection increases the risk during anti tuberculous chemotherapy. *Professional Med J.* 2014;21(1):49-54.
 14. Algerian Working Group/British Medical Research Council cooperative study. Controlled clinical trial comparing a 6-month and a 12-month regimen in the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis in the Algerian Sahara. *Am Rev Respir Dis.* 1984; 129:921–928.